

provide multiple benefits for biodiversity, people and climate. The new forest strategy ... will include a roadmap for planting at least 3 billion additional trees in the EU by 2030, in full respect of ecological principles. Tree planting is particularly beneficial in cities, while in rural areas it can work well with **agroforestry**, landscape features and increased carbon sequestration.”

EURAF [Policy Briefing #21](#) summarises the definitions of agroforestry used in the CAP Strategic Plans of Member States, but this briefing, back in September 20, summarised the EURAF Agroforestry Typology, and made a number of recommendations for its use in the Land Parcel Identification Systems of Member States.

2 What is agroforestry?

In the EU, agroforestry has a simple and flexible definition: “a land use system in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land” (Reg 1305/2013). This definition is complemented by Article 4 of the EURAF Constitution: “Agroforestry practices include all forms of association of trees and crops (silvoarable systems) and/or animals (silvopastoral systems), on a parcel of agricultural land, whether in the interior of the parcel or on its edges (hedges)”. National classifications of agroforestry are given in the CAP Strategic Plans of Member States are summarised in [Policy Briefing #22](#) and a “measurable” definition of agroforestry is proposed in [Policy Briefing #15](#) - i.e. “Agroforests” can be defined as “parcels classified as agriculture, including boundaries, with more than 5% tree-cover, or with tree-planting or management which is intended to exceed 5% cover. Shrubs may also be present”.

The EURAF Agroforestry Typology (Table 1) is based on Dupraz et al [\[1\]](#) and Mosquera-Losada et al [\[2\]](#). It recognises that all rural land in the EU is divided first into “agricultural land” and “forest land”, then classified into “arable land”, “permanent grassland” and “permanent crops”. This information is held in national Land Parcel Information Systems (LPIS), and data on land-use and crops in parcels and sub-parcels is supplemented with an GIS layer, which records “landscape features”. These must be on agricultural land and include hedges, individual trees, lines of trees and groups of trees. They have a measure of protection and do not detract from the eligible area used for the calculation of basic payments. Silvopastoral or silvoarable parcels may also be fully eligible for basic payments, depending on the threshold values used by Member States (MS) to scale-back payments according to the number of trees or their crown-cover. In normal circumstances, agricultural basic payments are not made for forest parcels, although in most countries these areas are eligible for assistance from CAP rural development budgets.

Table 1 The EURAF Agroforestry Typology

Tree location	Agroforestry System	Agroforestry Practice	
		Agricultural Land	Forest Land
Trees inside parcels	Silvopastoral agroforestry	1 Wood pasture	10 Forest grazing
	Silvoarable agroforestry	2 Alley cropping 3 Alley coppice 4 Food forests	4 Food forests
	Permanent crop agroforestry	5 Orchard cropping, 6 Orchard grazing.	
	Agro-silvo-pasture	7 Agro-silvo-pasture	
Trees between parcels	Tree Landscape Features (protected by CAP Conditionality Rules)	8 Woody-landscape-features	
Trees in settlements	Urban agroforestry	9. Settlement agroforestry	

Our Recommendations (September 2020):

1. In the new CAP, starting in January 2023, the eight agroforestry practices tabulated above should be included as IACS/LPIS codes,
2. Landscape features, and particularly tree–landscape-features should be marked on farm-orthophotos by Member States, and farmers asked to confirm their boundaries (as done by France in the previous CAP).²
3. Farmers should be reassured that Landscape Features are always fully eligible for basic payments.
4. IACS/LPIS returns should be used by MS for GHG Emissions Reporting to the EU and to the UNFCCC. MS could provide databases of estimated GHG emissions at least for NUTS4 municipalities, and potentially down to the level of individual farms. .

3 References

1. Dupraz C, Lawson GJ, Lamersdorf N, Papanastasis VP, Rosati A, Ruiz-Mirazo J. Temperate agroforestry: the European way. In: Gordon A, Newman SM, Coleman B, editors. Temperate Agroforestry Systems. CABI: Wallingford; 2018. pp. 98–152.
2. Mosquera-Losada MR, Freijanes JJS, Pisanelli A, Rois M, Smith J, den Herder M, et al. How can policy support the uptake of agroforestry in Europe? Cranfield University; 2017. Report No.: EU AGFORWARD Project - Grant No 613520. Available: https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/files/pub/docs/deliverable_8_24_how_can_policy_support_agroforestry1.pdf

² We totally agree with the WWF suggested Amendment to the SP Regulation Article 129 (3). “3. Existing up-to-date administrative registers such as the IACS, LPIS, animal and vineyard registers shall be maintained and reinforced. The IACS and LPIS shall be further developed to better meet the statistical needs of the CAP. By 1 January 2023, at the latest, all Member States shall have in their LPIS an updated layer with full territorial coverage for high-biodiversity landscape features. Data from administrative registers shall be used as much as possible for statistical purposes and to monitor compliance in cooperation with statistical authorities in Member States and with Eurostat.”